

Amerika Samoa Vs. The World

The Disproportionate Socioeconomic Burden in Conservation Borne By American Samoa as an Unrecognized Small Island Developing State under Colonial Rule.

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Abstract:

Action in 2023 by the Biden administration, under Presidential Proclamation 14008, to enclose and designate large areas in the Central Pacific Ocean (CPO) as National Marine Monuments (NMM) - federally protected ocean areas - posed an existential problem for American Samoa. These enclosures would effectively have closed all national fishing areas in reasonable proximity to American flagged tuna fishing vessels based out of Pago Pago. Such a closure would have then pushed fishing effort by these American Samoan based vessels out onto the High Seas, further exposing the fleet to foreign competition and increasing operating costs, with a feared result that the one remaining tuna cannery would be forced to close, devastating the already precarious state of the American Samoan economy, which relies almost entirely on the tuna fishing industry using the deep water harbor at Pago Pago.

The saga of American Samoa's struggles with the whims of Federal management, along with its lack of recognition as a Small Island Developing Territory, are starkly highlighted by this chain of events, providing very clear contextual evidence of the disproportionate burden in conservation that the Territory has been forced to bear as an unrecognized Small Island Developing State (SIDS) under colonial rule, and the lack of support the Territory has received, not only from the colonial center, but also, as a consequence of its colonized status, from its neighbors in the Pacific, compounding this lack of formal recognition as a SIDS.

This paper outlines how U.S. marine conservation policy in the Pacific, specifically the marine sanctuary expansions proposed under Proclamation 14008 – in 2025 overturned by an Executive Order signed by President Trump – can impose disproportionate socioeconomic costs on non-self-governing territories like American Samoa. Through a mixed-methods approach combining qualitative process-tracing and analysis of international fisheries affairs using the logic of tacit inference, this study reveals how American Samoa's subaltern status – denied both full domestic representation and international recognition as a Small Island Developing State (SIDS) – leaves it uniquely vulnerable to conservation mandates crafted by a distant metropole. The findings highlight a fundamental conflict between top-down global environmentalism based on privileged western-centric liberal ideals and the rights of marginalized territories, advocating for a justice-oriented approach that considers the aspirations of a developing economy, grants autonomy in fisheries management, and recognizes the unique plight of sub-national island jurisdictions such as Amerika Samoa.

Keywords: asymmetric power, decolonization, fisheries management, strategic risk, marine conservation, disproportionate burden, transboundary fisheries, high seas fisheries, ocean grabbing, UNLCOS, UNFSA, WCPFC, Pacific Forum, colonial conservation, dependency theory, American Samoa, 30x30, marine policy, environmental justice, 30 by 30 initiative

Introduction

In 2021 with the signing of Presidential Proclamation 14008 (Biden, 2021), United States of America (US) President Biden proclaimed the intention to create large National Marine Monument (NMN) sanctuaries in the Pacific Ocean, a step that would effectively close the bulk of the Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs) of the US Pacific unincorporated territories to commercial fishing. While, on the face of it, this policy seemed to be an important proactive step in satisfying the US Government commitment to global marine conservation, subject to the 30 by 30 initiative finally agreed at the COP15 meeting of the Convention on Biological Diversity in December 2022 (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2022), American Samoa, as a small and unincorporated US territory heavily dependent on the fishing industry as the cornerstone of its economy, was slated to bear the brunt of this commitment. The proposed closures would have resulted in the abrogation of fishing areas important to the economy of the Territory of American Samoa, with the resulting fear in the Territory, based on previous experience, that the single remaining tuna cannery in Pago Pago would be shuttered; decimating livelihoods, employment and socioeconomic development in American Samoa.

Proclamation 14008 can be seen, in this context, to be a veritable artifact of a dependent development paradigm (Singer, 1949; Prebisch, 1950; Dobb, 1963; Kvangraven et. al, 2017; Kvangraven, 2023), whereby a colonized subject is deliberately stripped of its capacity to develop economically to control the subject territory in perpetuity, dependent on welfare handouts from the metropole in order to afford daily life. Rather than being a simple policy misstep, Proclamation 14008 is identifiable as a contemporary manifestation of what Fanon (1961) identified as the inherent violence of the colonial project, in this case the restructuring of economies to serve the interests of the metropole while ensuring perpetual subjugation. The Biden proposal further offers contextual evidence of ocean grabbing (Bennett et al., 2015; Doerr, 2016) by a large, powerful, privileged actor to the detriment of a less privileged, less powerful actor. For American Samoa, a non-sovereign territory already struggling with geographic isolation, economic precarity, and lacking international recognition, Proclamation 14008 presented a dynamic that placed a further disproportionate and unjust burden on its people. The rescission of Proclamation 14008 (Economic Policy Institute, 2025) does not solve the underlying structural issue; it merely highlights how American Samoa's fate hinges on the volatile political whims of a distant metropole. American Samoa's conundrum is compounded by the consistent refusal of Commission members at the Western and Central Fisheries Commission (WCPFC) to recognize American Samoa as a Small Island Developing State (SIDS), in contravention of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea – UNCLOS (1982) and the United Nations Fish Stocks Agreement – UNFSA (1995).

This article focuses on providing an lego-economic perspective on the disproportionate burden faced by American Samoa in relation to marine conservation, informed by a post-colonial lens, framed by the logic of tacit inference (Polyanyi, 1966), and contextualized inference (Kintsch, 1998), to consider the implications of this burden, also touching on the implications of pushing commercial fishing effort out to the Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ), outside of sovereign control, while further considering the imposition of competition for economic resources with other fishing entities on the high seas at the margins of nationally administered EEZs. A lego-economic perspective lends itself to examining and hermeneutically understanding historical context, providing a solid basis for political realism. This approach can further inform us how we arrived at our current situation and enables us to offer grounded observations that problematize and guide further enquiry.

Methodology: A Hermeneutic Approach to Asymmetric Power

A paucity of historical socioeconomic research surrounding the local economy of American Samoa, along with a lack of an easily accessible public domain repository of economic data for the Territory, hampered the development of a quantitative research paradigm for this research. To create any meaning from scant evidential signposts scattered throughout a milieu of public records, this writer instead undertook an inductive approach to illicit and problematize subject areas for further enquiry and analysis. We therefore step out of a quantitative positivist approach to interrogate the assumptions of western-centric privileged state actors who focus on subjective normative realities formed from concepts that are psychological rather than logical, such as “understanding, belief and judgement” (Polanyi, 1966, p1). This anti-positivist position is held in communion with an explicit rejection of the logical positivist “assumption that the data and operations of mental processes are explicitly specifiable” (Polanyi, 1966, p12). For the same reason we also must reject a critical lens grounded in western-centric humanism as being deterministic and fixated on so-called objective normative reality, dominated as it is by a privileged western-centric discourse inappropriate to the hermeneutic foundation of the issue being examined. In the background we also draw upon post-colonial theory (Fanon, 1961; Said, 1978) to understand the discursive practices that legitimize this dispossession. The western-centric framing of vast marine protected areas (MPAs), as an unqualified protector of the global commons, erases the local understandings, lifeways and aspirations; instead representing a form of environmental imperialism (Duffy, 2013), whereby western-centric conservation ideals are imposed on the very local communities who are denied a vote at the top table.

To interrogate the philosophical paradigm tacitly observed in the actions of privileged actors in the context of international fisheries and international commons diplomacy, we examine the situation of American Samoa, focusing on the hermeneutics of the truth, unveiled as they are using Polyanyi’s theoretical tools of tacit awareness, incorporating historical analysis via the hermeneutics of artificial transformations of human societies through tacit knowing and integration of awareness, designed around extrapolating new knowledge based on implicit understandings of things as they are (Polyanyi, 1966). In this study, we are restricted to examining information available solely in the public domain; this paper is therefore an outsider analysis of a problem internal to the Samoan people and their relation to the US Federal polity, invoking Polyanyi’s logic of tacit inference to analyze the issues presented using a postcolonial, legalo-economic lens.

From Spanish Lake to American Ocean

The westward expansion of the United States of America (US) reached its zenith in the late 19th century, capped briefly by the full extent of empire at the conclusion of The Pacific War (1941-1945). In the wake of the Spanish American War of 1898, and with the conquest of Hawai’i by American businessmen from 1893 to 1898, the US gained a large empire in the Pacific Ocean, including the Philippines, Guam and several smaller outlying islands (Pratt, 1950). Interest in the islands of Samoa also peaked around the end of the 19th century, driven by an ideological consensus in Washington DC that colonial expansion to include territories in the Pacific was essential for economic growth and the protection of US shipping and business in the Pacific Ocean (Droessler, 2013). Indeed, around this time, US politicians first articulated the idea that the Pacific Ocean should be held as an “American Ocean, dominated by American commercial enterprise for all time” (Pratt, 1950 p31).

In 1899, the USA, the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Ireland (UK), and Germany reached a formal agreement to partition the islands of the Samoa group into a German Samoa and an American Samoa (Tripartite Convention of 1899). This agreement was concluded without consulting the Samoan people. Indicative of US priorities at the time, the islands of Tutuila and Aunu'u, after being formally ceded in 1900 by their matai – traditional rulers – were placed in the administrative care of the US Department of the Navy. In 1904 the islands of Ta'u, Ofu, Olosega, and Rose Atoll were added to the Territory (NOAA, n.d.). Under Navy administration until 1951 (Truman, 1951), American Samoa's value, as the only US territory in the Southern Hemisphere, was not economic, but geopolitical and martially strategic. The establishment of the Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) regime under the auspices of the United Nations Convention of the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS, 1982) meant the creation of large US EEZs for American Samoa and other nearby US remote territories – the Pacific Remote Islands (PRI) - initiating an economic boom for American Samoa to become a major tuna processing hub; at its height supplying 50% of canned tuna for the U.S. market. At peak around the turn of the 21st century, two large canneries operated side by side at Ānua on the northern side of Pago Pago harbor, with production guaranteed by a steady supply of skipjack tuna from American purse seine vessels fishing in the EEZs of American Samoa and the PRIs, supplemented by longliners and purse seine vessels flagged or licensed to neighboring countries landing in Pago Pago, including Asian fishing entities such as Japan and Taiwan. From 2007 to 2018 however, in the wake of a series of federal policy missteps and two natural disasters, the economy of American Samoa declined by 18 percent, which also led to a significant population decline (U.S. Government Accountability Office, 2020; Western Pacific Regional Fishery Management Council, 2018; Levine, 2009; American Samoa Government, 2025; Saliata, 2014).

In 2012 US President Obama declared a renewed strategic interest in the Pacific; at the same time specifically categorizing the US as a Pacific Nation, a stance which represented a significant shift in US policy to re-establish a more direct hegemony over the Pacific Ocean after decades of political neglect since the end of the Cold War (Droessler, 2013). This strategic move tacitly appears to have resulted in a decrease in the importance of trade and self-determination for the unincorporated Pacific territories from a US perspective, representing instead an increase in the militarized US projection of hegemonic power. This projection seems, in turn, to form part of a wider geopolitical game being played in the Asia-Pacific region by the US Federal Government, through successive administrations, as a form of competition based on the containment of the economic and strategic interests of rival Asian powers seeking influence over the region the US regards as the American Ocean.

Matching this US political objective of American hegemony over the Pacific with the growing voices of environmental lobby groups based primarily in privileged western countries aimed at 'protecting' the international commons and transboundary stocks of highly migratory species, tacit logic allows us to infer that the Biden Administration sought to gain political capital and soft power by meeting its environmental targets at the margin of its empire, leaving the metropolitan center untouched to carry on with an environmentally unconscious status quo, while consciously evading the real problem of environmental damage caused at the metropole, perhaps in order to maintain a voter base; thereby sacrificing the economic viability of colonized and disenfranchised unincorporated territories, including American Samoa. If we focus on the critical moment of Obama's Pacific Pivot (Droessler, 2013), it can be inferred that the proposed closures under Biden Proclamation 14008 are a direct consequence of this moment, at the same time enforcing the romantic ideal of an American Ocean as one of a series of moves toward hegemonic control of strategic and

economic resources of the Pacific via enclosure and closure of EEZs and pushing fishing effort out to the High Seas to the ABNJ; allowing us to infer a US determination to enforce its own sovereignty in international agreements. More research could uncover and elucidate this point, which is beyond the scope of this paper.

American Samoa's burden and double disenfranchisement

The position of American Samoa as an unincorporated territory of the US does seem to provide some advantages for its inhabitants in terms of access to the US for employment and education. There are, however, distinct and serious economic disadvantages for the territory held in common with other Pacific Island states, such as relative geographic isolation, lack of infrastructural connectivity, and reliance on one major industry – fishing – to generate societal income (U.S. Government Accountability Office, 2020). In addition, as a colonized territory with almost zero voice in federal and international fora – a double disenfranchisement – the needs and aspirations of American Samoa tend to be overlooked in the formulation of federal and international marine policy. Proclamation 14008 (Biden, 2021) must be understood within this framework, presenting a cruel irony: to meet a global conservation target, the Biden Administration proposed protecting ocean areas by closing them to the very industry that sustains its most economically vulnerable Pacific territory. An important immediate effect of such a closure is the eradication of fishing grounds deemed to be crucially important to viability of the one remaining tuna cannery at Pago Pago, and a resultant distinct possibility of the devastation of the economy of American Samoa if that cannery were to close. This projected outcome would likely have meant a death knell for the territorial economy, ensuring perpetual dependence on federal welfare (Cagurangan, 2023).

To elaborate, the last 25 years has seen a continuous decline in the population of American Samoa, from an historical high of 58,000 in 2001, to a population in 2024 of 47,000 (World Bank, 2025). This demographic decline alone indicates a contextualized inference of a lack of economic opportunity for the inhabitants of American Samoa leading to significant outmigration, with this situation also being compounded by an underdeveloped economy excessively reliant on diminishing returns from the tuna fishing industry, then needing state welfare assistance handed down from Washington DC. American Samoa is not, in this circumstance, able to control its own development, being drawn instead into a web of dependent development (Kvanraven, 2023; Kvanraven et. al., 2017; Dobb, 1963; Prebisch, 1950; Singer, 1949), nurtured by the US to be dependent in perpetuity. Such an outcome aligns perfectly with the concept of ocean grabbing, defined as the capturing of the control of decision-making around international fisheries and marine commons resources by powerful state actors, non-state commercial industrial fishing interests or conservation NGOs, to the detriment of smaller scale local users (Bennett et al., 2015). This situation further exemplifies the core critique in dependency theory whereby the metropole – the US – structures the economy of the periphery – American Samoa – to keep the periphery subservient, unable to achieve self-sustaining development (Kvanraven, 2023). Any benefits of this imperfect western-centric 'conservation'; international goodwill and progress on 30x30 metrics, accrue to Washington D.C., while the entire socioeconomic cost will be borne by American Samoa.

The practical implications of this type of marine closure are numerous. To outline just two examples:

Firstly, the Small Island Developing Territory of American Samoa is somehow expected to accept a disproportionate burden in the conservation and management of its marine domain

and economic fishing grounds, at least partly because it is not fully recognized as a Small Island Developing State (SIDS), and indeed is treated by many of its Pacific neighbors as somehow a proxy for US influence in the South Pacific subregion, incapable of asserting its own identity in regional bodies. This suspicion is borne out somewhat by the inability of American Samoa, as a non-sovereign territory, to vote in international forums such as the Western and Central Pacific Fisheries Commission (WCPFC). Additionally, as an unincorporated territory of the US, American Samoa has no vote in US Congress, being required therefore to negotiate its needs from a starting position of subordination, an occupied, colonized, and unrecognized state with very few real friends. This double jeopardy threat is further complicated by the complete lack of support for American Samoa by SIDS and other entities at international fora such as WCPFC, based on an articulated suspicion of the territory's occupied colonial status as a vassal of the United States of America, with the US being an imperial elephant in the Pacific Islands room. Indeed, American Samoa has consistently sought recognition as a SIDS within the WCPFC to address the disproportionate economic and regulatory burdens its fishing industry faces. The territory argues that its purse-seine fleet, vital to its tuna processing economy, should receive the same SIDS fleet benefits, such as exemption from certain high seas effort limits, granted to other small island states (Western and Central Pacific Fisheries Commission, 2023; Western Pacific Regional Fishery Management Council, 2023; Western Pacific Regional Fishery Management Council, 2022; American Samoa Department of Marine and Wildlife Resources, 2016). The Territory's recognition as a SIDS/Participating Territory in the WCPFC Convention provides a legal foundation for its arguments (Western and Central Pacific Fisheries Commission, 2004), but political and economic subjective 'realities' have prevented the translation of this status into practical fishing benefits, with some Pacific SIDS seeking to limit fishing on the High Seas to drive economic benefit from access fees and resource rentals into their domestic EEZs. (Western and Central Pacific Fisheries Commission, 2021; Pacific Islands Forum Fisheries Agency, 2020; Sangaalofa Clark et.al., 2022).

Secondly, because the Territory is not properly recognized as a SIDS, the clauses of UNCLOS and UNFSA that mandate special consideration for SIDS and Least Developing Countries (LDCs) are overlooked in the consideration of policy and conservation measures, and the resultant socioeconomic effect on the Territory is ignored. In international and federal policy American Samoa tends to be lumped together with the US, its policies dictated by, or overridden by federal policy. A serious ongoing economic threat to American Samoa can therefore be tacitly grounded in the extremely asymmetrical power relationship the Territory is required to negotiate with the US Federal Government, with the Territory often not heard in federal matters, and with federal rules often applied to American Samoa without regard to the special needs and less developed situation of the Territory, as is clearly demonstrated in the summary reports emanating from the WCPFC. The federal deaf ear has, historically, negatively affected the development of a competitive and sustainable economy for American Samoa, for example when the US Federal Government extended the mandate for a minimum wage to the Territory in 2007 against the advice of Samoan advisers. This mandate led, in turn, to a major economic downturn for the Territory, an economic problem exacerbated by an international economic downturn and a natural disaster in 2008-2009 (U.S. Government Accountability Office, 2020; Fair Minimum Wage Act, 2007). Dependency theory explains this situation well (Dobb, 1963; Kvangraven et. al., 2017); over time, terms of trade for American Samoa have deteriorated to the point that the Territory has become an increasing recipient of US Federal welfare funding (U.S. Government Accountability Office, 2020). The US government, while generally supportive of the Territory's SIDS quest in principle, has been slow to fully endorse American Samoa's status as a SIDS in the WCPFC. The US's

broader regional role, including support to client states via federal aid and defense agreements, sometimes contributes to complex political dynamics, impacting the level of engagement and advocacy for American Samoa's claims in multilateral fisheries negotiations (Western Pacific Regional Fishery Management Council, 2023).

One direct consequence of the Fair Minimum Wage Act was the closure of the Chicken of the Sea cannery in 2009, resulting in a loss of at least 2000 jobs in a territory within a population of only 57,000 people (U.S. Department of Labor, 2010; U.S. Government Accountability Office, 2020). The closure directly resulted in a significant decline in economic revenue, measured as a direct loss excess of five million dollars (USD) of income annually to the Territory through utility payments from the cannery, but also in the money no longer spent in the territory by vessel operators and fishing companies, leading to significant decreases in job opportunities, household incomes, and domestic expenditure. In this context a federal mandate ignoring the advice of affected stakeholders stole economic growth from American Samoa, ensuring only ongoing dependent development with Federal Assistance in its wake. With Proclamation 14008, Samoans were once again faced with a political decision made in Washington significantly affecting the lives of people in American Samoa, without reference to, nor in consultation with, the people most affected. This conundrum is nothing new; as "American Samoans have exercised agency in the face of hegemonic political practices characterized by imperial amnesia and territorial disenfranchisement" (van der Elsen, 2020, iii) over the entire period of occupation and colonization since 1899. The will of the American Samoan people, it seems, is often ignored, rebuffed, or overridden, with agency over resources subject to the whim of political winds unrelated to American Samoa and its development.

Analysis: Amerika Samoa vs. the World

Amerika Samoa holds a unique position in the US polity. The Territory is unincorporated, similar to other places such as Guam or Puerto Rico, but American Samoans are also not regarded as US citizens, being instead the only group of non-citizen U.S. Nationals. Here exists a tacitly observed perception of a deliberately authored acknowledgement that the people of American Samoa are a colonized people, somehow foreign to the American polity in location, culture, language, and ethnicity (Morrison, 2013). Indeed, since 1946, American Samoa has been listed by the United Nations as a Non-Self-Governing Territory (United Nations, n.d.). In this context, American Samoa also faces suspicion from other Pacific SIDS as being under US influence and having no voice of its own. However, the Territory continues to exert agency opportunistically through cooperation with the US Federal Government, while experiencing many of the same developmental issues experienced by recognized SIDS. (van der Elsen, 2016; American Samoa Department of Marine and Wildlife Resources, 2016; Western and Central Pacific Fisheries Commission, 2023; Western and Central Pacific Fisheries Commission, 2024, Ahrens, et. al., 2023).

A central issue is that American Samoa is neither independent, nor recognized as a developing state, even though it is clearly a territory in development. This assertion is borne out by the ongoing rejection of repeated requests by American Samoa to be recognized at WCPFC as a SIDS, despite a clear legal foundation for this aspiration. Further, the economy of the Territory is subordinate to the policy whims of the US Federal Government as a non-voting subject. Favorable outcomes may only be negotiated through the acquiescence of federal officials to the voices of the American Samoan people, who nevertheless have continued to openly articulate their needs since colonization. Such an outcome was recorded

in early 2025, when President Trump rescinded Proclamation 14008 (Economic Policy Institute, 2025).

American Samoa's art of articulation is well illustrated in the records of WCPFC Annual Commission meetings, as is the indifference of Commission Members, including SIDS, to the special rights and needs of American Samoa as a Small Island Developing Territory under colonial control. (Western and Central Pacific Fisheries Commission, 2023; Western Pacific Regional Fishery Management Council, 2023; Western Pacific Regional Fishery Management Council, 2022; American Samoa Department of Marine and Wildlife Resources, 2016; Haas, Azmi, & Davis, 2024). Any imposition of Presidential will on the people of American Samoa, even if described in terms of a commitment to green policy as a good international corporate citizen, constitutes a significant socioeconomic threat to the Territory of American Samoa and its people, having the corollary effect of passing any commitment by the US to adopt green governance out to the very margins of empire, in order not to affect the day-to-day status quo of the American center, resulting in zero change in environmental performance in the mainland United States, and further raising the specter of economic collapse and dependence in perpetuity for the Samoan people in Amerika Samoa.

Cynically, one might infer that the policy articulated by the Biden administration would have resulted in pushing fishing effort out of nationalized EEZs and into the ABNJ, thereby allowing the US to shore up and claim further catch history on the High Seas, as part of a great ocean grab (Bennett et al., 2015, Doerr, 2016), locking up resources inside EEZs and exploiting the international commons as a privileged actor. This cynicism is compounded by the refusal of Commission members to accept the vastly underprivileged position of American Samoa as a SIDS because it is viewed as a colonial outpost of an empire – the USA – being treated with a great deal of suspicion by many Pacific SIDS, in part also perhaps due to reluctance in American Samoa to fully sever colonial ties with the US (Anderson, 1978; Bennett et.al., 2015; Sailiata, 2014; Aiono, 2023). Indeed, the US is aware of the reliance of American Samoa on the High Seas (Haas, Azmi, & Davis, 2024; Michal, 1992), with any enclosure of monuments adjacent to American Samoa having the potential to force American flagged, American Samoan based, vessels to operate essentially as High Seas only fleets, competing at the margins of large spatial exclusion zones, with negligible resulting benefit to pelagic fisheries conservation. A return to some type of pre-Obama status quo, viz-a-viz American EEZ areas relatively adjacent to American Samoa allowed to be fished, offers an opportunity for the territory to rebuild its economy. The reversal of Proclamation 14008 does not, however, address the failure of the Pacific Forum, Pacific Forum Fisheries Agency (FFA) member states, the WCPFC and the US Federal Government to address the needs of a colonized Small Island Developing Territory, in direct contradiction of the stated goals and aspirations of those organizations.

Given that American Samoa has been on the United Nations list of Non-Self-Governing Territories since 1946 (United Nations, 2024), the actions of the Biden Administration may be cynically viewed as the actions of a colonial power to restrict the ability of a colonial territory to establish a basis for economic independence from the center, serving to entrench territorial dependency, rather than supporting the concept of self-determination of the American Samoan territorial government over its economy and internal self-governance. The 2025 political reversal of the national monument proclamations of previous US Presidents reverts American Samoa to a previous status quo, although immense damage to the American Samoan economy has already occurred which will temper, at least initially, any investment to

rebuild local capacity. This economic opportunity is further tempered by the central problem of how to recognize American Samoa appropriately in the international marine space.

Although there is scant economic data available for American Samoa before the year 2000, we are able to track the effects of cannery closures in the 21st century from publicly available records, allowing us to consider the effects of the Fair Minimum Wage Act 2007, the 2009 Samoa Earthquake and Tsunami, and Cyclone Ola of 2018, all of which, perversely, led to a significant injection of Federal financial stimulus into American Samoa (U.S. Government Accountability Office, 2020; Rudman & Grimes, 2008; American Samoa Department of Commerce, 2019; Moliga & Lafaele, 2019; OECD, 2023). The potential economic implications of a national sanctuary closure are illuminated by the previous experience of the closure of the Chicken of the Sea cannery as a direct consequence of the Fair Minimum Wage Act (2007), and also by the startup and closure of a state-of-the-art tuna Tri Marine cannery in a single year – 2016 (American Samoan Government, 2018). Increases in Federal assistance quite clearly demonstrates dependent development in action.

The situation of American Samoa is, therefore, a microcosm of a global injustice, exposing the tendency of wealthy, powerful nations to outsource the burdens of environmental conservation to marginalized communities and foreign fishing zones, played out as a textbook case of the asymmetric imposition of the will of the privileged center to use less privileged peripheral territories as sacrificial zones for virtue-signaling policies. In the context of American Samoa, the hermeneutic applied to the problem raised in this paper incorporates an implicit understanding of the nature of asymmetrical power relationships, highlights limited sovereign control by American Samoa over its own economic base – being unincorporated as an aspect of political realism exposed by American apathy – placing political process before effective management of resources; in turn leading to inefficient solutions that penalize a colonized or neo-colonized margin without disrupting the unsustainable behavior of the metropole/center. Securing fishing rights to the High Seas through the type of sanctuary policy proposed by Biden (2021), a matter criticized by Doerr (2016) as one of multiple crises of neoliberalism, becomes a burning current issue in the globalization of marine economics, highlighting as it does a determinist view of Fisheries Management imposed asymmetrically by the United States of America and the other large Distant Water Fishing Nations (DWFNs) operating in the Pacific, dispossessing and appropriating fisheries resources to the detriment of Pacific SIDS and Territories, and impinging on the planning and implementation of Blue Ocean economic development policies based on ancestral perspectives and community-based natural resource governance. (Okafor-Yarwood et. al., 2022; Hanich et. al., 2021; Pouponneau, 2023; Roscher et. al., 2023; Lannon, 2023; Food and Agriculture Organization, 2014; Pacific Islands Forum Secretariat, 2021; World Bank, 2025; Doerr, 2016; Haas et. al. 2023).

In the words of then American Samoan Director of Fisheries and Wildlife Management, Archie Soliai (Western Pacific Regional Fishery Management Council, 2023):

“The highest priority for American Samoa is to gain full recognition of the disproportionate burden we have borne as a SIDS / Participating Territory, and to maintain a reliable supply of tuna for processing in our one remaining cannery”

This request is completely reasonable and rational. However, the lack of support among Pacific SIDS at the Western and Central Pacific Fisheries Commission (WCPFC) for this logical step casts a pall on the integrity of the mantra of Pacific Unity espoused by sub-

regional organizations such as the Pacific Forum (Pacific Islands Forum Secretariat, 2014) and its subsidiary body FFA, an integrity already seriously compromised by the factionalism evident in the relationships fostered via the workings of the Parties to the Nauru Agreement (PNA). As Tamate (2013, p67) explains:

“While the Parties to the Nauru Agreement have effectively unified control over the valuable tuna resources within their EEZs, internal divisions frequently arise from competing national interests, external diplomatic influences, and differing economic strategies. This factionalism challenges the notion of a monolithic Pacific regional fisheries governance, revealing instead a complex interplay of cooperation and exceptionalism that sets the PNA apart from broader Pacific fisheries bodies like the FFA. The presence of non-Pacific advisers further complicates decision-making processes, sometimes embedding agendas that do not fully align with all member states' interests.”

PNA exceptionalism vis-à-vis the wider Pacific fisheries governance framework, compounded by external influences from Australia and New Zealand via bilateral treaties and the involvement of non-Pacific technical advisers (Macdonald, 2024), sustains factionalism both within the PNA and in relation to the rest of the Pacific region. This situation, which we can tacitly infer to be a psychologically constructed normative reality, hampers the acceptance of American Samoa's request for recognition as a SIDS at WCPFC. Waning US influence in the region, due to long term neglect of key relationships with Pacific Island countries and latent and latent anti-Americanism articulated by former colonies in the North Pacific – personally observed by this writer as a professional practitioner in Fisheries Management in the Pacific region – also exacerbates the disproportionate socioeconomic burden in conservation borne by American Samoa as an unrecognized small island developing state under colonial rule, a situation only partly relieved by the rescission of Proclamation 14008 in early 2025. American Samoa's pursuit of SIDS recognition at the Western and Central Pacific Fisheries Commission is a compelling example of power exercised not as domination but as positive, relational agency (Fussell, 2025). In seeking equitable regulatory treatment reflective of its unique status, the Territory navigates complex regional and international power dynamics, coordinating dialogue and alliances to influence fisheries governance. This quest reveals both the enabling capacity and constraints that power embodies, as the territory strives to align regional cooperation with its economic and social needs amid the competing interests of sovereign states and major powers.

Conclusion

The reversal of Proclamation 14008 is a temporary reprieve, not a solution. Without a fundamental re-evaluation of the asymmetric relationship between American Samoa and the US, the Territory will remain a pawn in a game of geopolitical and environmental chess, its people continuing to bear the disproportionate socioeconomic burden of an empire's inconsistent whims. The situation borne by American Samoa is a microcosm of the global injustice perpetrated by western-centric determinism: the tendency of wealthy, powerful state and non-state actors to outsource the burdens of environmental conservation to the less privileged, most marginalized communities. The task becomes, how to disabuse the US of the notion of using its territories as sacrificial zones for virtue-signaling policies? How also, do we frame policy solutions that will deliver a win-win scenario for both the Federal Government and the Territory of American Samoa?

First and foremost, as an outsider, this writer wishes to clearly state the view that effective policy solutions must be primarily authored by the people of American Samoa themselves, rooted in the self-determined needs and aspirations of the Territory and its native inhabitants. With fisheries and marine resources being vital to local livelihoods, economic survival, and cultural identity, administrators must therefore recognize multiple knowledge and legal systems, community needs, and power relations to enable genuinely effective fisheries governance. Such an approach builds trust, accountability, and equitable participation among diverse stakeholders in the pluralist relationship that the Territory navigates through its geopolitical reality with the US Federal Government. Additionally, American Samoa has the right to expect unconditional support from Pacific Islands SIDS in its quest for recognition, especially when considering that those same SIDS were, with one exception, former colonies of metropolitan imperial powers who therefore might be expected to understand the needs and aspirations of the Territory regarding sustainable multigenerational socioeconomic development and full membership of the Pacific family of nations and territories.

In view of these challenges, possible pathways forward include the following suggestions:

1. Autonomy and Recognition:

Granting American Samoa autonomy over the management of its EEZ and championing the formal recognition of American Samoa as a Small Island Developing State (SIDS) within regional fisheries governance bodies such as the WCPFC are critical first steps.

2. Equitable Consultation:

Establishing a mandatory, legally binding consultation process for any federal policy affecting the territory's economy is a further crucial step to avoid economic collapse caused by federal over-reach in its quest for virtue-signaling international policy engagements. Federal policies should evolve, therefore, to mandate legally binding, meaningful consultation processes with Territorial representatives prior to the enactment of conservation or economic regulations affecting the Territory. This type of consultative framework is vital to avoid past mistakes that have led to severe economic downturns, such as the impacts following the Federal imposition of 2007 Fair Minimum Wage Act.

3. Transitional Measures:

If conservation closures are deemed necessary in the future, the federal government should institute comprehensive transitional measures. Such measures must include, not the provision of aid welfare, but rather full economic restitution and robust investment in diversified sustainable economic alternatives designed and led by local stakeholders. Such support can help break the entrenched cycle of dependency on welfare handouts from the metropole by fostering economic resilience and sustainable multigenerational socioeconomic development as a tacit pathway to an eventual decolonization of the Territory as a developed economy.

4. Confronting Dependency:

The U.S. might consciously work to break the cycle of dependency it has created by supporting genuine, locally led economic development. Ultimately, addressing American Samoa's disproportionate burden within the broader frameworks of geopolitical and environmental governance requires an ethical recalibration: a commitment to justice and equity that moves beyond superficial conservation metrics to prioritize the voices and agency of colonized and marginalized peoples. The Territory's future hinges on transforming current power asymmetries into partnerships of trust and shared purpose to create a model for the

Pacific in reconciling environmental stewardship with human dignity, self-determination, and multigenerational sustainable development.

The plight of American Samoa exemplifies the broader injustices faced by all dependent territories whose economic futures are continually shaped by distant powers imposing environmental and political agendas without adequate consultation or consideration of local realities. The reversal of Proclamation 14008 offered temporary relief but failed to address systemic inequalities inherent in the US-Territory relationship, thereby perpetuating economic dependency and political disenfranchisement. American Samoa's struggle to gain recognition as a Small Island Developing State in the Western and Central Pacific Fisheries Commission reflects the persistent marginalization of colonized territories in global conservation and governance frameworks.

Moving forward, meaningful change requires a genuine partnership that respects the internal sovereignty, voice, and knowledge of the Samoan people. Only through equitable recognition, autonomous management of marine resources, and inclusive regional cooperation can American Samoa begin to break the cycle of dependent development and achieve sustainable socioeconomic growth. Addressing these challenges is not just an imperative for environmental protection but a test of justice for marginalized communities bearing disproportionate burdens. The world's commitment to conservation must be matched by a commitment to equity, dignity, and self-determination for all peoples.

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